

Characterization of Interface Structure in
Gr/Al and Gr/Mg Composites

S.P. Rawal
Martin Marietta Denver Aerospace
P.O. Box 179
Denver, CO

and

L.F. Allard*
American Cyanamid Company
Stamford, CT

and

M.S. Misra
Martin Marietta Denver Aerospace
P.O. Box 179
Denver, CO

ABSTRACT

The interfacial bond integrity, dislocation substructure and precipitate morphology in the interfiber matrix region in diffusion bonded Gr/Al Gr/Mg and cast Gr/Mg composites were examined by transmission electron microscopy. Gr/Al composites exhibit three different precipitate morphologies (blocky, lath-shaped and fine cuboidal of similar chemical composition), and Gr/Mg composites show both spherical and lamellar $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ precipitates. Interface structure in diffusion bonded composites did not show any voids and reaction compounds. Whereas, cast Gr/Mg composite revealed patches of microvoids sporadically near the interface, along with Mg_2Si and MgO phases formed due to the chemical interaction between the matrix and SiO_2 fiber-coating. Both Gr/Al and Gr/Mg exhibited a high density of dislocations which can be attributed to the differential contraction between the fiber and matrix during fabrication process. Dislocation substructure in diffusion bonded Gr/Mg composites was mostly linear, whereas diffusion bonded Gr/Al and cast Gr/Mg exhibited dense dislocation tangles. These observations of high dislocation density, associated residual stress state, and morphology and distribution of second phase precipitate may suggest the fundamental mechanisms to explain the damping behavior and dynamic dimensional stability of metal matrix composites.

* Presently at Martin Marietta Energy Systems, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN

INTRODUCTION

The interface is a necessary link between the fiber and matrix to accomplish the efficient load transfer in composites. Often the fibers are chemically treated or alloying elements in the matrix are added to achieve wettability and the required bond. But the nature of the bond between the coating or metallic matrix and high modulus graphite fiber is primarily governed by available bonding sites (e.g., defects or domain edges) on the fiber surface [1]. Graphite fibers seem to have low defect density and low fiber surface energy which may limit the wettability and thus be a critical factor influencing ultimate strength and properties of graphite reinforced composites.

In addition, interface region is characterized by a high dislocation density, which can be attributed to large differences of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the matrix and fibers [2, 3]. Such difference in CTE between Gr fiber ($-0.7 \text{ ppm}/^{\circ}\text{F}$) aluminum alloy ($13 \text{ ppm}/^{\circ}\text{F}$) or magnesium alloy matrix ($14 \text{ ppm}/^{\circ}\text{F}$), contribute to a residual stress state and associated high dislocation density. In essence, the nature of bond, residual stress state and chemical stability in the interface region may significantly influence the mechanical behavior of metal matrix composites.

The purpose of this study was to characterize the interface structure, i.e., second phase precipitate morphology, interfacial compounds, and dislocation substructure in Gr/Al and Gr/Mg composites by transmission electron microscopy.

MATERIAL

Three types of composite specimens were examined: Diffusion-bonded Gr/Al and Gr/Mg and a cast Gr/Mg specimen. Both continuous fiber-reinforced Pitch 55 Gr/6061 Al and Pitch 100 Gr/AZ91C/AZ31B Mg single-ply [0] panels were prepared by state of the art diffusion bonding technique. The fiber volume in Gr/Al composite was 39%, and 26.5% in Gr/Mg composite.

The cast P100 Gr/AZ91C Mg composite specimen was fabricated by using the filament winding vacuum casting process [4]. These test specimens had [+16°]s lay up and 39.8% fiber volume. A major distinction between the diffusion bonded and cast composite is that graphite fibers in diffusion bonded case have a chemically vapor deposited Ti-B coating, while in cast Gr/Mg specimens, they have an air stable silicon di-oxide (SiO_2) coating.

TEM SPECIMEN PREPARATION

An ion milling technique was used to prepare thin foil specimens for examination by TEM. First, 5 mm wide slices of original plate were cut and epoxied together to create a sandwich of three bulk slices, all oriented so that the fiber axes were parallel. From these sandwiches, 300 microns thick wafers were cut using a slow speed diamond saw, such that plane of section was normal to the plane of original plate, and fibers were extended in the plane of wafer. These sections were precision ground to a thickness of about 100 microns and then dimple-ground to form a specimen nominally 20 microns thick at the center of dimpled region. A single hold graphite washer was then attached to the dimpled specimen, using Torr-seal epoxy with a 24 hour cure, to provide support for the delicate

specimens during further handling. Finally, these specimens were milled to perforation in a Gatan Duo-ion mill, using 5kV argon ions at 12 degrees incident angle. These conditions were found to be critical, and would often produce many interface regions in a typical specimen which were electron transparent in both the graphite fiber and matrix regions. Care was taken during all stages of the specimen preparation process to ensure that mechanical deformation or specimen heating which might change bulk dislocation structures would be minimized. The thinned specimens were observed in a Philips 420T transmission electron microscope, operating at 120 kV or in a JEOL 2000 FX operated at 200 kV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The shape, size and distribution of second phase precipitates adjacent to fiber-matrix interface affects the role of matrix in the failure mechanisms of a composite. These precipitates act either as a source of dislocation-generation or as a barrier to dislocation motion. Also, in the presence of fiber-coating, pressure, temperature and time conditions during consolidation or casting process may lead to the formation of an interfacial compound, which will affect interfacial strength. For example, Gr/Al specimens heat treated at temperature above 550°C, show the formation of aluminum carbide and aluminum oxycarbide at the interface, which eventually leads the degradation of graphite fibers (5)

PRECIPITATE MORPHOLOGY:

Three different precipitate morphologies are observed in Gr/Al composites: large blocky, lath-shaped and cuboidal. In a narrow inter-fiber matrix region shown in

Figure 1
Precipitate Morphology in Diffusion Bonded Gr/Al Composites (a) Large Blocky Precipitate (Point A), Lath-Shaped Precipitate (Point B) and (b) Cuboidal Precipitate

Figure 2
Typical EDS Spectrum Obtained from Large Blocky Precipitate in Gr/Al

Figure 1a, blocky precipitate (point A) and lath shaped precipitate (point B) are evident at the interface; and a cuboidal precipitate is visible after tilting the specimen to matrix [001] zone axis orientation as shown in Figure 1b. The EDS spectra obtained from three types of precipitates revealed that each contains Si, Cr, Mn, Fe and Cu; and a typical spectrum of a large precipitate is shown in Figure 2.

In the case of diffusion bonded Gr/Mg composites, TEM images of narrow inter-fiber matrix regions generally reveal spherical

Figure 3
Aluminum-Rich Spherical Precipitates Mixed with Lamellar Precipitates in Wide Matrix Regions of Diffusion Bonded Gr/Mg

shaped precipitates, which in wider matrix regions ($> 10 \mu\text{m}$) are mixed with lamellar precipitates, as shown in Figure 3. EDS spectra of both spherical and lamellar shaped precipitates show them to be aluminum rich and consistent with the $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ phase.

Various TEM images of both diffusion bonded Gr/Al and Gr/Mg did not exhibit any reaction compound at the

interface. Also, the examination of a number of different interface regions confirmed the presence of a thin Ti-B coating on the graphite fiber and absence of any voids at the interface.

The interfiber matrix regions of cast Gr/Mg composites primarily show lamellar shaped $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ precipitates. In addition, several blocky precipitates are seen along the fiber matrix interface, as shown in Figure 4A. These precipitates have some evidence of faceting typical of a large single crystal grain structure. Also, dislocations are common within the blocky precipitate. TEM images of this region at different tilts show relatively sharp, straight boundaries in the matrix, perhaps corresponding to low angle subgrain boundaries. An EDS spectrum obtained from the large precipitate shows (Figure 4b) a Mg:Si ratio consistent with a Mg_2Si composition. The inset electron diffraction pattern from the precipitate further confirms that it is a cubic Mg_2Si precipitate. The EDS spectrum acquired from the matrix adjacent to these precipitates showed no silicon in the matrix.

The formation of Mg_2Si precipitate results from the chemical reaction between the SiO_2 coating and magnesium-rich matrix. Adjacent to these blocky Mg_2Si precipitates as seen at points A and B in Figure 5a, are also seen very fine-grained polycrystalline structures which appear to be "nodules" on a similar polycrystalline layer about 50 nm thick at the fiber-matrix boundary. Electron diffraction results and EDS analyses (Figure 5b) indicate that both the nodular structures and the interface layer are essentially MgO. This layer is also formed due to the chemical reaction between the matrix and coating. Figure 5a also shows microvoids present near the interface in the cast Gr/Mg composite. Though the formation of

Figure 4a
 Blocky Precipitates at the Fiber-Matrix Interface in Cast Gr/Mg Showing Evidence of Faceting Typical of Large Single Crystal Grain Structure. The Inset Electron Diffraction Pattern Obtained from the Blocky Precipitate Confirms it is a Cubic Mg_2Si Precipitate

Figure 4b
 EDS Spectrum Obtained from the Blocky Precipitate Present at the Interface in Cast Gr/Mg

Figure 5a
 Interface Region in Cast Gr/Mg Composite Showing Microvoids, Large Blocky Precipitates (A and B) and Fine Grain Polycrystalline Structure (C). The Inset Electron Diffraction Pattern Obtained from the Fine Grain Structure (MgO)

Figure 5b
 EDS Spectrum Obtained from the Fine Crystalline Structure Present at the Interface in Cast Gr/Mg

Mg_2Si and MgO at the fiber matrix interface is thermodynamically favorable and is a necessary consequence of achieving wettability between the matrix and fiber, their effect on microstructural integrity and strength still needs to be evaluated [6, 7]. It must be noted that mechanical properties of cast Gr/Mg composites match very well (95%) with the values predicted by composite theories [4]. If reaction phases at the fiber-matrix interface do not degrade the composite strength, then size and distribution of Mg_2Si precipitates may even play a beneficial role in the damping behavior of cast Gr/Mg composites [8].

DISLOCATION SUBSTRUCTURE:

In Gr/Al composites, a typical interface region exhibits dense and tangled dislocations in the adjacent matrix region, as shown in Figure 6. The thin dark band directly at interface is the original Ti-B coating applied on the graphite fiber. Obviously, these dislocations remain in and out of contrast depending upon the specimen orientation (with respect to the electron beam) for imaging microstructural features.

Similarly, an interface region in diffusion-bonded Gr/Mg composite shows dense dislocation substructure in the adjacent matrix. Figure 7 shows that most of these dislocations are linear rather than tangled, and seem to bear a crystallographic orientation. The significant differential contraction between the fiber and matrix during the consolidation process leads to a residual stress state in the interface region and a consequent high density of dislocations. These differences in tangled and linear dislocation substructures are likely due to available slip

Figure 6
Dense Dislocation Tangles in the Matrix Region Adjacent to the Fiber-Matrix Interface in Diffusion-Bonded Gr/Al

Figure 7
Typical Dislocation Substructures Near the Fiber-Matrix Interface in Diffusion-Bonded Gr/Mg

systems in aluminum and magnesium matrix. The average dislocation density in both Gr/Al and Gr/Mg composites is $4 \times 10^{14} \text{ 1/m}^2$.

Dislocation configuration near the interface in cast Gr/Mg composites is quite different than diffusion bonded Gr/Mg composites, as shown in Figure 8. Here, the areas in dark contrast show a high density of entangled dislocations and an interference effect at the low angle subgrain boundaries. It is speculated that dislocation tangles are related to the combined effects of residual stress state (generated due to differential contraction between fiber and matrix) and stresses induced by the growth of large precipitates. It is likely that fabrication conditions in casting process are sufficient to activate basal and

Figure 8
Regions in Dark Contrast Showing High Density of Dislocation Tangles Adjacent to the Fiber-Matrix Interface in Cast Gr/Mg

pyramidal slip systems in Gr/Mg composites. In the literature, the average dislocation density measured near the reinforcement-matrix interface SiC_w/Al and Gr/Al composites seems to be consistent with the values predicted by a breakaway dislocation damping mechanism envisioned by Granato-Lucke (G-L) model [9, 10, 11]. These observations of high dislocation density, associated residual stress state, and fine precipitate (or impurities) in the matrix region adjacent to the interface seem to provide an evidence for the G-L model, which states that beyond a critical dynamic stress amplitude, dislocations breakaway from the pinning points and contribute to hysteretic energy losses.

CONCLUSIONS

Interface structure in both diffusion-bonded Gr/Al and Gr/Mg, and cast Gr/Mg composites, was successfully characterized by transmission electron microscopy. Gr/Al composites exhibit three types of precipitates: large blocky, lath-shaped and fine cuboidal; and Gr/Mg composites typically exhibit spherical and lamellar shaped precipitates. Diffusion bonded composites do not indicate any interfacial reaction, whereas cast Gr/Mg composites show the formation of Mg_2Si and MgO at the interface due to the chemical reaction between the fiber-coating and matrix. Measurements of strength and modulus of cast Gr/Mg composites suggest that interfacial compounds do not seem to degrade the microstructural integrity. Both diffusion bonded and cast composites reveal a high dislocation density in the matrix region adjacent to the fiber matrix interface which is probably caused by the residual stress state generated due to differential contraction between the fiber and matrix during fabrication process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the Office of Naval Research Contract N00014-84-C-0413. The authors wish to acknowledge Dr. Steven G. Fishman for various technical discussion and continuing support and encouragement.

REFERENCES

1. Lee, R.N., Carbon-Fiber Surface Defect Structure: Consequences for Composite Materials, J. Mater. Res. (in press).
2. Arsenault, R.J. and Shi, N., Dislocation Generation Due to Differences Between the Coefficients of Thermal Expansion, Mat. Science and Eng., 1986, 81, 175-187.
3. Chawla, K.K., and Metzger, J. Mater. Sci., 1972, 7, 34.
4. Misra, M.S., Rawal, S.P. and Jackson, J., Novel Processing Techniques to Fabricate Gr/Mg Composites for Space Applications, Martin Marietta Aerospace, Denver, CO, Phase I Technical Report MCR-85-711, November, 1985.
5. Marcus, H.L., Interface Character of Aluminum-Graphite Metal Matrix Composites, Report UTMSE-83-1, University of Texas, Austin, 1983.
6. Dr. H. Katzman, private communication.
7. Dr. D. Goddard, private communication.
8. Steckel, G. Mechanical Damping Behavior of Gr/Mg Composites, Aerospace Corporation, El Segundo, CA, ONR Report TOR-0084-A-5726-01 (-1), October, 1985.
9. Hartman, J.T., Jr., Keine, K.H., Armstrong, R.J. and Wolfenden, A., Dislocation Density Determination in Composites, Journal of Metals, April 1986, 33-35.
10. Rawal, S.P., Armstrong, J.H., Misra, M.S., Dislocation Damping in Gr/Al Composites, to be presented at 116th TMS Annual Meeting, February, 1987.
11. Granato, A.V. and Lucke, K., Theory of Mechanical Damping Due to Dislocations, J. Appl. Phys., 1956, 27(6), 583-593.